

Review on Comparative Analysis and Design Using WSM And LSM Method

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Abstract— A STAAD-Pro plate girder analysis assessment will concentrate on evaluating the documentation's clarity and thoroughness as well as the analysis results' accuracy, consistency, and dependability. It is imperative to guarantee that the analysis sufficiently considers the varying load performance of the plate girder by using working state method and limit state method offers practical insights for optimizing the design or, if necessary, modifying. So, the number of research papers are reviewed to study the analysis and design the structure subjected to various load.

Keywords— Plate Girder, Analysis, Design IS 800:2007, IS 800:1984

I. INTRODUCTION

People feel the need for bridges, and they transmit this need to the government through public representatives, or the government recognizes the value of bridges. The government chooses to build a bridge at a specific area as a result of the increasing traffic demand, which may be caused by a number of factors, including a major road, a tourist destination, a center for pilgrimage, industry, etc. a structure that allows cars to move safely and smoothly over a body of water, traffic, or another impediment. Nonetheless, a wide range of other constructions are typically regarded as highway bridges.

Plate girders are typical I-beams composed of individual structural steel plates; the vertical web and horizontal flanges are formed together by welding, bolting, or riveting the beam. Currently, an I section with three to two flange plates and one web plate is welded and built appropriately. Plate girders are typically preferred for larger spans made with the provision

of extra cover plates. A plate girder has extensive flexural strength; the resistance to bending and shear can be Done.

The web, which is a thin plate that buckles under strain, can be prevented by adding web stiffeners in both the horizontal and vertical planes. These days, only welded plate girders which are more visually pleasing and lightweight than riveted or bolted plate girders—are constructed. The parts of a plate girder are as follows: Web plate (i) and flange plate (ii) Stiffeners (iii), flange plate and web splices (iv), and end connections (v).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kalyanshetti, M.G. (2013): The distribution of the live load in the longitudinal girders and the bending moment due to the live load in the slab and girders have been calculated and finalized. The distribution of load is determined using the Courbons method. Here, we test the effectiveness of the Courbons hypothesis by changing the spans of the number of longitudinal girders.

Sandesh Upadhyaya K (2016): In this paper, a deck slab system with span lengths of 20, 24, and 28 meters is compared and contrasted. Conventional designs were created using Excel sheets. Shear force and bending moment values are investigated. The live load is designated as a wheeled Class AA vehicle. Finite element analysis and the manual Courbons approach are compared for verification. It proves that standard slabs on girders are less effective than T beam slabs.

Tangudupalli (2017): This study compares loadings, approaches, and the same bridge using STAAD Pro V8i software.

The girder is analyzed using the three rational techniques (Hendry Jaegar, Guyon-Massonet, and Courbons theory). The ones that have been assigned are Class A, Class AA, Class 70-R, and Class-B IRC loadings. Included are the loadings for Saudi Arabia, AASHTO, and British Standard, among other nations.

Ahmed Abrar (2017): The work's objective is to identify the optimal section for bridges with different spans. The job is to design and evaluate sections for different types of I.R.C. vehicles.

The working stress technique and Courbons theory are utilized to validate the structural analysis performed by the Csi Bridge Program. It is clear that the vehicle designated as I.R.C. 70-R has the most impact. T beam girders work well

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for bridges with a maximum span of thirty meters; lengths greater than that make them impractical. Box girders are suitable for larger spans.

Using IS 800: 2007 and IS 800: 1984, M. Krishnamoorthy and D. Tensing studied the design of columns with both ends fixed based on strength to weight ratio and load carrying capacity against various sections for column lengths of 2 m, 3 m, and 4 m. In order to present similar results utilizing graphs for various concepts, the researchers in this study manually created column members using FOS and load combinations using the appropriate design procedures. Consequently, it was shown that WSM has a slightly higher percentage of load-carrying capacity than LSM and that weight per unit length controls the strength-to-weight ratio [2].

For bridge modeling, Staad Pro software is utilized, and for analysis, the grillage approach is applied. Four lanes with different spans of fifteen, twenty, thirty, and thirty meters are examined using IRC class A loads. Furthermore, there are variations in the number of longitudinal girders. Studies reveal that the Courbons method causes an increased bending moment in exterior beams. The problem with the exterior girder overestimating its load

According to research by Hanady A. El-rahman El-Dehemy (2020), the most it is possible to manufacture plate girders with no web stiffeners, equal-sized flanges, and minimum mass.

Like a rolled I-section, a section with a deeper modulus will weigh less than a section with a shallower modulus, with the exception of deeper sections that need for a thicker web. A wider flange plate is required to withstand the buckling propensity when the compression flange is laterally unconstrained. However, because of the challenges encountered in assembling the technique, the cost will go up.

According to Jurnal Kejuruteraan et al. (2020), steel plate girders are vulnerable to shear and local buckling because of the nature of their webs. Traditionally, this has been avoided by providing vertical stiffeners at predetermined intervals. The inclusion of inclined stiffeners not only

increases the girder's strength but also enables the beams to support different loads within the structure.

Gollangi and Datta (2019) conducted research on steel plate girders, a structural element that finds extensive use in various fields, mostly in long span railway bridges due to its many advantageous qualities.

In most cases, plate girders are built for bending and shearing. The moment resisting capacity of the plate girders is situated between truss girders and rolled I-sections. They consist of assembled flexural members. Their bending capacity can be raised by extending the space between the flanges. As the web area grows, this also raises the shear capacity. Only when the plate girder's self-weight is at minimum can economy be realized.

CONCLUSION

The investigation mentioned above leads to the following findings. A code of practice guarantees security by outlining specific minimal requirements for the design. This document presents significant clauses from IS 800-1984 and IS 800-2007.

The new IS 800 – 2007 code for plate girder design is far more efficient than the previous one. Because the IS 800 - 2007 code incorporates additional provisions and advances sustainable design, it is appropriate for the state of design practice today. Most designers and construction authorities primarily use the most recent code of practice.

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